

Development, validation, and application of an innovative UHPLC-Orbitrap-HRMS method for multi-class analysis of endocrine disruptors in bottled water: Influence of bottle material, water source, and retail price

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Development of a high-throughput SPE-UHPLC-HRMS method for quantifying 25 EDCs and screening 983 suspects in bottled waters.
- Validation showing high accuracy, precision, and EU-compliant uncertainty with detection limits below regulatory thresholds.
- Identification of 17 EDCs in 37 bottled waters, with plastics more contaminated and suspects linked to packaging, drugs, and cosmetics.
- Observation that mineral waters contain higher α -zearalanol levels than spring waters, indicating source-dependent mycotoxins.
- Evidence that higher retail price correlates with increased phthalate levels, challenging assumptions of exposure equity.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Handling Editor: Dr. L. Liang

ABSTRACT

Background: Endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) are linked to chronic conditions such as hormonal cancers, metabolic disorders, and reproductive dysfunction. They can enter drinking water through inadequate wastewater treatment and poor waste disposal, contaminating surface and groundwater. Bottled water adds risk due to

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2025.344995>

Received 8 October 2025; Received in revised form 4 December 2025; Accepted 6 December 2025

Available online 9 December 2025

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Keywords:

Multi-class EDCs
UHPLC-Orbitrap-HRMS
Bottled water
Water source
Retail price
Plastic vs. glass

leaching of packaging chemicals, especially from plastics. Since even low-level exposure may harm health, systematic monitoring is crucial. This requires advanced analytical methods able to detect and quantify multiple EDC classes at trace concentrations in bottled drinking water.

Results: This study developed and validated a comprehensive multi-residue method to quantify 25 EDCs across eight chemical classes - hormones, microbial agents, mycotoxins, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, phenols, phthalates, and sunscreen agents - and to screen 983 additional suspected EDCs in drinking water. The method, based on solid-phase extraction coupled with ultrahigh performance liquid chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry, was optimized using factorial design to ensure accuracy and reliability. Validation with still water demonstrated excellent linearity ($R^2 \geq 0.99$), low detection limits ($0.5\text{--}5.0 \text{ ng L}^{-1}$), and compliance with international criteria for recovery, precision, and measurement uncertainty. Cross-validation on sparkling water further confirmed robustness, with only 17β -estradiol showing slightly elevated recovery at the lowest concentration. Stability tests showed analytes remained intact for 72 h under dark conditions. Application to 37 Belgian bottled waters revealed 17 EDCs, with bisphenol B and acetaminophen most abundant. More compounds occurred in plastic than glass bottles, while mineral water showed higher α -zearalanol than spring water. Notably, premium plastic bottled water contained increased phthalate levels.

Significance: This study presents a robust method for multi-class EDC analysis in bottled drinking water, offering high sensitivity and broad coverage, including EU watch list substances. Using an extensive suspect screening database from international inventories, it is the first Belgian study to map diverse EDCs in popular bottled water brands. The findings provide crucial data for public health risk assessment and inform regulatory and commercial decisions, emphasizing packaging, source type, and retail price as key factors.

1. Introduction

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), endocrine disrupting compounds (EDCs) are substances that may alter one or more functions of the endocrine system, and consequently cause adverse health effects in an intact organism or (sub)populations [1]. A wide variety of compounds have been pertained to having endocrine disrupting properties, including certain natural and synthetic hormones, personal care products, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, phenols, phthalates, polyhalogenated compounds and mycotoxins [2,3]. Most EDCs interact with the effects of lipid (steroidal sex) or amino acid-derived (thyroid) hormones, while a few interact with peptide/protein hormone synthesis or signaling, resulting in a variety of chronic complex diseases including metabolic disorders, hormonal cancers, reproduction problems, neurotoxicity, cardiovascular diseases, immune effects, etc. [4,5].

Environmental EDC loadings in drinking water have been largely attributed to the deficiency of wastewater and sewage treatment plants, as well as improper waste disposal, followed by contaminated surface and groundwater [6]. Because of their incomplete removal due to their wide-ranging nature and properties, these compounds remain in different environmental media, such as soil, water and sediments, especially among the water cycle (wastewater-aquatic systems-drinking water), with bioaccumulation and biomagnification throughout the food chain [2,7], and adverse human health effects have arisen because drinking water has become an additional route of human EDC-exposure [2]. Additionally, drinking water packaging has added to the risk by allowing EDCs to migrate into the water [8,9]. It is worth noting that concentrations of EDCs in drinking waters are often in the low ng L^{-1} range. However, as hormone-related cancers, such as breast and testicular cancer, are known to arise from exposure to EDCs even at low concentration levels, environmental EDC concentrations in water supply systems are of great interest, as they pertain to human health [2].

Despite efforts to regulate EDCs in cosmetics, biocidal products, and foods, environmental contamination by these substances continues to rise [10–12]. While some individual EDCs are regulated in drinking water (bisphenol A and atrazine at maximum limits of 2.5 and $0.1 \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ respectively, in Europe) [12–14], there is no comprehensive international regulation in place specifically targeting EDCs as a distinct category, although filling the knowledge gap of EDC exposure has been highlighted as one of the priorities by the European Union (Horizon Europe Program 2021, EU Drinking Water Directive) [15,16] and WHO [17], amongst others. Additionally, in 2020 the European Commission established a watch list of substances and compounds of concern for

water intended for human consumption in which two EDCs have been additionally included, *i.e.* 4-nonylphenol and 17β -estradiol at maximum guidance values of 300 and 1 ng L^{-1} , respectively [18].

Quantifying EDCs in water remains analytically challenging due to their typically low environmental concentrations, wide chemical diversity, and broad range of polarities [19]. Existing studies have demonstrated that ultra-high-performance liquid chromatography (UHPLC) coupled with mass spectrometry (MS or MS/MS) provides superior sensitivity compared to alternative techniques such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) or gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) [19]. High-resolution mass spectrometry (HRMS), in particular, has emerged as a powerful tool by enabling non-targeted or suspect screening approaches. This allows for the detection of both known and unknown ionizable compounds without the need for prior analyte selection or authentic reference standards [20]. Consequently, HRMS-based workflows have been increasingly adopted to address the complexity of EDC mixtures present in environmental and drinking water samples.

Despite these advances, several analytical challenges persist. Most existing studies have focused on targeting specific EDC chemical groups or compound classes [21–24], and only very few studies have been performed using UHPLC-HRMS methods [25–27] (Table 1). Comprehensive methods capable of simultaneously quantifying multiple EDCs across diverse chemical families - while also screening for hundreds of additional suspects - remain scarce [28] and are insufficiently sensitive to tackle low EDC concentrations in drinking water and/or impractical due to large initial sample volumes and long runtimes (Table 1). Furthermore, studies integrating these approaches with comparative assessments of bottled water types, packaging materials, and economic factors are absent in the literature.

To address these gaps, the present study introduces a comprehensive and high-throughput analytical workflow that combines targeted quantification of 25 EDCs from eight distinct classes (hormones, microbial agents, mycotoxins, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, phenols, phthalates, and sunscreen agents) with suspect screening of 983 additional EDCs at high sensitivity. The method employs solid-phase extraction (SPE) coupled to UHPLC-HRMS, optimized and validated for both still and sparkling bottled drinking water. To the authors' knowledge, this represents the first application of such an integrated targeted-suspect screening approach in Belgium. A total of 37 commercially available bottled waters, sourced from supermarkets and beverage distributors across Flanders, were analyzed. The study further investigates correlations between EDC occurrence and factors such as bottle material (glass vs. plastic), water source (mineral vs. spring), and

product cost, the latter serving as a proxy for packaging quality.

By extending analytical coverage and integrating economic and packaging variables, this work advances beyond previous studies that were limited in scope, compound range, sensitivity and feasibility. The resulting dataset provides critical baseline information for future risk assessments, regulatory decisions, and public health evaluations concerning consumer exposure to EDCs in bottled drinking water.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Targeted EDCs

Twenty-five EDCs were retained based on existing literature and the EU 2022 EDC List I, which identifies substances recognized as endocrine disruptors [29]. During the selection, chemicals with potential impacts on human health were prioritized, particularly those associated with breast and prostate cancer [30,31], Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease [32,33], type 2 diabetes [34], obesity [35], thyroid disorders [34,36,37], reproductive impairment & male infertility [34,38,39], abnormal pregnancy outcomes and precocious puberty [40]. Selection also considered the prior detection in Flanders' drinking water supply [41], increasing prevalence due to climate change [42,43], and relevance as components of packaging or water pipe materials [9,44], ensuring representative coverage of various EDC classes (Table S1).

2.2. Chemicals and reagents

Twenty-three analytical reference standards for targeted analysis, as well as 10 analytical reference standards for confirmatory analysis following suspect screening, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Overijse, Belgium), whilst zearalenone and its metabolite α -zearalanol were supplied by Fermentek (Jerusalem, Israel). A wide range of

compound polarities was included (log P from -0.2 to 7.5), encompassing key EDCs from different origin such as hormones ($n = 6$), microbial agents ($n = 1$), mycotoxins ($n = 2$), pesticides ($n = 4$), pharmaceuticals ($n = 5$), phenols ($n = 4$), phthalates ($n = 2$) and sunscreen agents ($n = 1$) (Table S1). The selected internal standards ($n = 11$) (Table S1) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Overijse, Belgium), except for zearalenone- $^{13}\text{C}_{18}$, which was provided by Fermentek (Jerusalem, Israel). All standards were dissolved in methanol (MeOH), except for atrazine, bisphenol A, bisphenol B, chlorothiazide and the estrogens, which were dissolved in MeOH/dimethylsulfoxide (80/20, v/v) to reach a primary stock solution of 1 mg mL^{-1} . Standard work solutions were prepared in acetonitrile (ACN), thereby reaching a concentration between 0.01 and $100 \text{ } \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$. Using the latter, standard mix solutions were established in ACN at concentrations between 10 and $1000 \text{ } \mu\text{g L}^{-1}$. All stock and work solutions were stored in 10 mL amber glass bottles at $-20 \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$. The organic solvents were of LC-MS grade, purchased from Fisher Scientific (Loughborough, UK). Formic acid (98 %) and ammonium solution (NH_4OH , 25 %) for analysis, and hydrochloric acid (HCl, 37 %) for extraction experiments, were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). The Oasis® Hydrophilic-Lipophilic-Balanced (HLB) SPE cartridges (500 mg, 6 mL) were purchased from Waters (Zellik, Belgium). The glass microfiber filters ($0.45 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, $90 \times 90 \text{ mm}$) for extraction optimization experiments were obtained via Whatman™, GE Healthcare Life Sciences (Buckinghamshire, United Kingdom). Ultra-pure (UP) water was obtained by usage of a purified-water system (VWR International, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany).

2.3. Instrumentation

2.3.1. Instrumental optimization

The software program JMP 12.0 was used in a similar manner as during the extraction optimization to fit, assess, and model a statistical

Table 1

Comparison of the newly developed UHPLC-HRMS method with UHPLC-HRMS methods from literature on the measurement of multi-class EDCs in drinking water. Distinct contributions of this study relative to prior work are emphasized in bold.

	<i>This study</i>	<i>Huysman et al. 2017 [26]</i>	<i>Tröger et al. 2018 [27]</i>	<i>Zhanget al. 2024 [28]</i>
Method	SPE-UHPLC-HRMS	SPE-UHPLC-HRMS	SPE-UHPLC-HRMS	SPE-UHPLC-HRMS
Matrix	Drinking water – still & sparkling	Drinking water – still	Drinking water - still	Drinking water – still, waste water
Sample volume (L)	0.5	2.5	1.0	2.0
SPE sorbent	Oasis HLB	H ₂ O-phillic divinylbenzene Speedisks	Oasis HLB	Oasis HLB
Chromatographic column	Hypersil Gold (1.9 μm , $100 \times 2.1 \text{ mm}$) + Hypersil Gold (1.9 μm , $50 \times 2.1 \text{ mm}$)	Hypersil Gold (100 $\text{mm} \times 2.1 \text{ mm}$; 1.9 μm)	ESI-: Acquity UPLC BEH C18 (2.1 \times 100 mm, 1.8 μm) ESI+: Acquity UPLC HSS T3 C18 (2.1 \times 100 mm, 1.8 μm)	Acquity UPLC BEH C18 (1.7 μm , 2.1 \times 150 mm)
Ionization	ESI	APCI	ESI	ESI
MS Device	Q-Orbitrap Exploris™	Q-Orbitrap Exactive™	Waters Xevo G2-S QToF	Q-Orbitrap Exactive™
Analysis time (min)	10	12.5	21	55
EDC compounds (n)	25	70	91 ^b	52
Classes (n =)?	Hormones, microbial agents, mycotoxins, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, phenols, phthalates and sunscreen agents (n=8)	Hormones (n = 1)	Pesticides, pharmaceuticals, personal care products, drug related compounds, food additives and perfluoroalkyl substances (n = 6)	Hormones, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, phenols and phthalates (n = 5)
LOD (ng L⁻¹)	0.5–5.0	0.06–5.00	0.1–170	n.a.
LOQ (ng L⁻¹)	1–5	0.13–5.00	n.r.	20,000
Recovery range (%)	94.4–113^a	95–109	0–96.6	50–120
Precision range (%)	<18.2 ^a	<10.5	n.r.	n.r.
Measurement uncertainty (%)	4.4–35.5	n.r.	n.r.	n.r.
Non-targeted or suspect screening?	Yes (983 Suspects)	No	No	Yes (Non-target)

Note: SPE = solid phase extraction; U(H)PLC = ultra(high) performance liquid chromatography; HRMS = high-resolution mass spectrometry; HLB = hydrophilic lipophilic balance; BEH = Ethylene Bridged Hybrid; ESI = electrospray ionization; APCI = Atmospheric pressure chemical ionization.

n.r. = not reported.

^a for within- and between-day values together.

^b Only 91 of 134 targeted compounds exerted a recovery >50 %.

screening design (*Fractional Factorial Resolution*), aiming to develop the most optimal instrumental method across 18 experiments (Table S2) [45]. Again, the core method was adopted from Huysman et al. (2019) [46] and 6 parameters related to chromatographic separation (*i.e.* starting conditions of the mobile phases) and mass spectrometric detection (*i.e.* capillary temperature, column temperature, auxiliary gas flow, sweep gas flow, and maximum injection time) were selected based on additional literature [26,47] and assessed for their impact. For these experiments, 150 μL injection solvent (ACN/UP water, 95/5, v/v) was spiked with a mixture of 25 EDCs to achieve a concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, which closely corresponds to the vial concentration after sample enrichment. Using the summarized normalized areas, t-ratios were obtained via JMP software analysis, with a t-ratio exceeding 1.96 in absolute value indicating a significant difference between groups at the 95 % confidence level. Annotation was based on the *m/z*-value, retention time (RT) and ^{13}C -isotope profile (^{13}C -isotope and stable ^{12}C -ratio). Additionally, MS/MS fragmentation at 3 collision energies (30, 50, and 70 eV) was performed on standard mixes at 100 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, to confirm compound annotation and establish the most optimal fragmentation patterns. A mass deviation of ≤ 1 ppm, a RT shift of up to 2.5 %, and a minimum signal-to-noise ratio of 10 was applied to reduce noise misidentification [48,49].

2.3.2. Finalized instrumental method

Chromatographic separation of EDCs was achieved using an Ultimate 3000 XRS UHPLC system (Dionex, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) equipped with a Hypersil Gold C₁₈ 100 \times 2.1 mm UHPLC column (1.9 μm particle size) (Thermo Fisher Scientific®, Merelbeke, Belgium) operating at 40 °C. Additionally, a Hypersil Gold trap column (1.9 μm , 50 \times 2.1 mm) (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Merelbeke, Belgium) was placed between the UHPLC pump and the injection valve for retarding phenols and phthalates originating from the mobile phase and analytical instrument. The injection volume was 2 μL . The mobile phase consisted of a mixture of UP water (mobile phase A) and ACN (mobile phase B) both containing 0.1 % NH_4OH , pumped at a flow rate of 0.3 mL min^{-1} . A short run time of 10 min was established with a linear gradient program as follows: 0.0–1.0 min: 5 % B; 1.0–2.0 min: 40 % B; 2.0–2.3 min: 90 % B; 2.3–6.1 min: 96 % B; 6.1–8.0 min: 96 % B; 8.0–10 min: 5 % B.

The full-scan HRMS and MS/MS analyses were carried out on an Orbitrap Exploris 120 MS (Thermo Fisher Scientific®, Waltham, MA USA), fitted with a Heated Electrospray Ionization (HESI-II) source, operating in both positive and negative mode. Nitrogen sheath gas, auxiliary gas and sweep gas flow were set at 30, 15 and 2 arbitrary units (a.u.), respectively. The vaporizer and capillary temperature were both 350 °C, and the spray voltage 3.5 kV or -3.5 kV in positive or negative ion modes, respectively. The optimal MS parameters were S-lens RF-

Table 2

MS data of the 25 targeted EDCs, detailing their main ion, collision energy (CE), and the accurate masses of both precursor and product ions (M1 and M2).

EDCs	Main ion	Precursor ion	M1	M2	CE
Hormones					
Estrone	[M – H] [−]	269.1547	145.0659	143.0503	60–70
17 α -Ethinylestradiol	[M – H] [−]	295.1704	159.0815	145.0659	60–70
17 β -Estradiol	[M – H] [−]	271.1704	183.0815	145.0659	60–70
Progesterone	[M+H] ⁺	315.2321	297.2214	109.0648	30–50
Testosterone	[M+H] ⁺	289.2162	109.0648	97.0648	30–40
Microbial agent					
Triclosan	[M – H] [−]	286.9439	147.9517	35.7150	10
Mycotoxins					
Zearalenone	[M – H] [−]	317.1395	175.0400	131.0503	50–60
α -Zearalanol	[M – H] [−]	321.1707	277.1810	202.0789	50–60
Pesticides					
Atrazine	[M+H] ⁺	216.1018	174.0542	96.0557	50–60
DEET	[M+H] ⁺	192.1383	119.0493	91.0543	30–70
Fipronil	[M – H] [−]	434.9315	329.9593	249.9585	30–40
Propiconazole	[M+H] ⁺	342.0771	158.9765	69.0699	30–40
Pharmaceuticals					
Acetaminophen	[M+H] ⁺	152.0706	110.0602	93.0336	50–70
Carbamazepine	[M+H] ⁺	237.1022	194.0965	179.0730	50–70
Chlorothiazide	[M – H] [−]	293.9414	213.9609	178.9921	60–70
Citalopram	[M+H] ⁺	325.1711	262.1029	109.0449	40–50
Propranolol	[M+H] ⁺	260.1645	183.0805	116.1071	50–60
Phenols					
Bisphenol A	[M – H] [−]	227.1078	212.0844	133.0659	50–70
Bisphenol B	[M – H] [−]	241.1446	212.0844	147.0816	50–60
4-Dodecylphenol	[M – H] [−]	261.2221	202.0789	133.0660	60–70
4-Nonylphenol	[M – H] [−]	219.1754	147.0815	133.0659	60–70
Phthalates					
BBP	[M+H] ⁺	313.1428	149.0236	91.0544	30–40
DBP	[M+H] ⁺	279.1591	149.0233	121.0285	50–70
DCHP	[M+H] ⁺	331.1901	167.0340	149.02340	30–40
Sunscreen agent					
3-4-MBC	[M+H] ⁺	255.1743	212.1197	105.0699	50–60
IS					
Acetaminophen-d ₄	[M+H] ⁺	156.0957	114.0852	96.0746	60–70
Butyl 4-hydroxybenzoate-ring- $^{13}\text{C}_6$	[M – H] [−]	199.1705	135.0453	98.0469	60–70
Citalopram-d ₆	[M+H] ⁺	331.2088	262.1030	109.0449	50–60
Cortisol-9,11,12,12-d ₄	[M+H] ⁺	367.2381	331.2208	121.0649	30–50
Diethyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d ₄	[M+H] ⁺	227.1835	153.0486	125.0599	30–40
Estrone-2,3,4- $^{13}\text{C}_3$	[M – H] [−]	272.1949	202.0788	148.0760	60–70
17 α -Hydroxyprogesterone-2,2,4,6,6,21,21,21-d ₈	[M+H] ⁺	339.2166	113.0900	100.0837	30–40
Isoproturon-d ₆	[M+H] ⁺	213.1869	171.1400	78.0821	30–40
Phenol-2,3,4,5,6-d ₅	[M – H] [−]	100.0801	71.4024	–	70
Propranolol-d ₇	[M+H] ⁺	267.2086	189.1181	116.1071	30–50
Zearalenone- $^{13}\text{C}_{18}$	[M – H] [−]	335.1998	185.0736	169.0467	50–60

Note: DEET = diethyltoluamide, BBP = benzyl butyl phthalate, DBP = dibutylphthalate, DCHP = dicyclohexyl phthalate, 3-4-MBC = 3-4-methylbenzylidene-camphor.

level 50, operated in polarity switching mode. The scan range was set between 60 and 900 Da at a resolution of 120,000 FWHM (Full Width at Half Maximum) and a rate of 1.5 Hz for full scan, and 70,000 FWHM for MS/MS analysis. A minimum of 10 data points per peak was chosen to guarantee accurate peak shapes and reproducibility of analysis – with values ranging between 12 and 18 data points per peak [50]. The automatic gain control (AGC) was set at 3×10^5 and the maximum injection time was set at 50 ms. Collision energies varied between individual compounds, ranging from 50 to 70 eV (Table 2). Instrumental calibration was performed prior to analysis to guarantee accuracy (mass deviations ≤ 1 ppm) of mass measurements. A ready-to-use calibration solution was injected, containing a mixture of 16 highly pure, ionizable components (m/z 50–3000 Da) designed for both positive and negative ionization (Thermo Fischer Scientific, San José, CA, USA). At the start and finish of the analytical run, a mixture of the 25 selected analytical standards was injected to verify the device's operational conditions and to obtain data for later identification of these analytes in the samples. Chromatograms of each EDC are presented in Fig. S1.

2.4. Sample preparation

2.4.1. Optimization of sample pretreatment

2.4.1.1. Still water. The software program JMP 12.0 (SAS Institute Inc, Cary, USA) was used to fit, assess and model a statistical screening (*Full Factorial Resolution*) design to develop the most efficient sample pretreatment (8 experiments, see Table S3). The core method, including the type of SPE cartridge and used elution solvent, was adapted from the previously published approach by Huysman et al. (2019) [46], and additional literature [25–27]. However, based on this, 3 parameters potentially influencing the peak areas during sample pretreatment, including extraction, were selected and evaluated for their impact, *i.e.* filtration using a glass microfiber filter, acidification with 1 mL HCl to pH 6, and the type of reconstitution solvent ([ACN/UP water, 95/5, v/v] or [MeOH/UP water, 40/60, v/v]). For these experiments tap water (pH = 7.0) was used, spiked with a mixture of 25 EDCs to achieve a concentration of 100 ng L⁻¹. Optimization was conducted by considering the summarized normalized area, emphasizing the number of analytes detected while ensuring an even distribution across compound classes. T-ratios were obtained as part of the analysis, with a t-ratio exceeding 1.96 in absolute value indicating a significant difference between groups at the 95 % confidence level. JMP software facilitated the process by automatically managing the underlying statistical calculations, including structuring the full factorial design and verifying assumptions such as normality and equality of variances [45].

2.4.1.2. Sparkling water. Based on literature, 4 additional sample preparation steps were evaluated as part of the extraction optimization for sparkling water [51–53]. These included degassing for either 5 or 20 min, with or without acidification using 0.1 % formic acid, followed by the optimized extraction protocol for still water. Again optimization focused on the summarized normalized areas, prioritizing analyte count and balanced compound class distribution.

2.4.2. Finalized sample pretreatment protocol

A disposable HLB SPE cartridge (500 mg, 6 mL, Waters) was used to clean up and concentrate 500 mL water samples. The cartridge was preconditioned with 6 mL of 5 % ACN in UP water followed by 7 mL of plain UP water. Samples were loaded under vacuum. For sparkling water samples, ultrasonication for 5 min was performed prior to extraction. After loading, the cartridge was washed with 8 mL of UP water and dried under vacuum for 20 min. Analytes were eluted with 9 mL ACN acidified with 0.1 % formic acid. The eluate was evaporated until dryness under a gentle nitrogen stream at 40 °C in a water bath. Reconstitution was performed using 150 μ L of ACN/UP water (95/5, v/v), corresponding to

500 mL of sample (*i.e.* a concentration factor of 3333). Finally, samples were vortexed for 5 min and the clear supernatant was collected into glass LC-MS vials and stored before analysis within 24 h.

2.5. Method validation on still water

To date, directive 2009/90/EC is currently the only European guideline available for the chemical evaluation of water quality [54]. It specifies that measurement uncertainty (U) must be below 50 %, and the limit of detection (LOD) must be at least 30 % lower than the environmental quality standard (EQS), the latter defined as the concentration of a substance in water that should not be exceeded to meet environmental quality objectives. For EDCs in aquatic environments, EQS values are only specified for atrazine (0.6 μ g L⁻¹) and 4-nonylphenol (0.3 μ g L⁻¹). To address the lack of analytical performance criteria for EDCs in drinking water, additional guidelines, such as Directive 2002/657/EC [55] and the SANTE 11312/2021 guidance [56], were consulted to ensure a comprehensive and robust validation of the proposed analytical method. The optimized analytical method was validated using various fresh tap water samples, that showed to be blank for the compounds of interest. The method's performance was evaluated based on linearity, LOD, limit of quantification (LOQ), within-day and between-day precision, within-day and between-day apparent recovery (R_{app}), U, carry-over, and specificity. A threefold 9-point calibration curve (0, 1.0, 5.0, 10, 15, 25, 50, 80, 100 ng L⁻¹) was constructed, and linearity was evaluated on 3 different days using the coefficient of determination (R^2) and the goodness-of-fit coefficient (g) (%), the latter addressing the difference between the nominal calibration curve value and the calculated concentration. The acceptance criteria for R^2 and g were established at ≥ 0.99 and ≤ 20 %, respectively [55,57].

The LOD was determined as 3 times the standard deviation of the y intercept divided by the average slope of 3 individual calibration curves within a linearity range of 1.0–100 ng L⁻¹. Additionally, blank samples were spiked at LOD level for each target compound and identity was confirmed by the typical fragmentation pattern (Table 2), as well as the presence of a ¹³C-isotope and stable ¹³C/¹²C-ratio. The LOQ was established by analyzing the lowest concentration which met the criteria for R_{app} and precision as outlined in the guidelines above. Values of R_{app} (%), *i.e.* ratio of the measured concentration to the theoretical (spiked) concentration, was assessed by analyzing 4 samples spiked at concentrations of 1.0 or 5.0 ng L⁻¹ (LOQ), 25 ng L⁻¹, and 50 ng L⁻¹. According to the Directive 2002/657/EC acceptance criteria for within-day and between-day R_{app} are between 50 and 120 %, however, to ensure rigorous validation, more stringent acceptance criteria were applied, *i.e.* between 70 and 120 %, as proposed by the SANTE 11312/2021 guidance [56]. Within-day precision (repeatability) and between-day precision (reproducibility) were assessed by calculating the relative standard deviation (RSD, %) for the 3 spiked concentration levels over 3 consecutive days. A maximum RSD of 20 % was deemed acceptable for validation [55,56]. The U was calculated similarly to previous studies [58,59] by multiplying the combined standard uncertainty (u_c) by a coverage factor of $k = 2$, ensuring a confidence level of approximately 95 %. Carry-over was assessed by injecting 3 solvent samples (ACN/UP water, 95/5, v/v) after the highest calibrator. Ideally, no peaks at the analyte's RT should be detected, but if present, the peak response should not exceed 10 % of the mean peak area of the analyte at the LOQ [55]. Finally, specificity was first evaluated in UP water and then confirmed by ensuring no interfering chromatographic peaks within a 5 % RT margin for all target compounds at their accurate mass in 3 tap water samples that were blank for the compounds of interest [55,56].

2.6. Method cross-validation on sparkling water

A preliminary study was conducted on three sparkling water brands to determine background levels of the target compounds. One brand was found to be suitable, showing no detectable levels for 24 out of the 25

compounds. The only exception was dibutyl phthalate, detected at 5.32 ng L⁻¹; replicate results for this compound were corrected accordingly. The method's applicability to sparkling water was evaluated by assessing within-day R_{app} and precision, using four replicates spiked at concentrations of 5.0 ng L⁻¹, 25 ng L⁻¹, and 50 ng L⁻¹. This was carried out using the same procedure and acceptance criteria established for still water, in line with the SANTE/12682/2019 guideline for cross-validation [60].

2.7. Sample storage stability

The storage stability of the selected 25 EDCs was evaluated at two concentration levels (25 and 50 ng L⁻¹, n = 3) in blank tap water. To confirm the absence of any target compounds and validate the sample blanks, an initial subsample was analyzed immediately before spiking. Spiked tap water samples were then stored at 4 °C in the dark and analyzed 72 h later. Each 500 mL sample underwent extraction and analysis as previously described for still water. Storage stability, expressed as recovery (RST), was assessed following the method of Kruve et al. (2015) [61] (Eq. (1)):

$$\text{RST (\%)} = \frac{S_{72h}}{S_{ref}} \times 100 \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Where S_{ref} is the peak area of the compound analyzed immediately after spiking, and S_{72h} is the peak area of the compound analyzed after 72 h of storage in the dark at 4 °C.

2.8. Application to bottled water samples

A total of 37 commonly consumed 1.5 L bottled still water samples were identified through an online survey conducted among 302 individuals from the Flemish population, using Qualtrics (Qualtrics, Provo, UT, USA) (Table S4, Fig. S2). The 37 samples, consisting of 20 plastic and 17 glass bottles, were collected between November 2023 and May 2025 from 10 different supermarkets and beverage distributors across Flanders, Belgium (Table S5). The selection included both mineral (n = 26) and spring water (n = 11). According to European legislation, spring water is natural water sourced from an underground spring, bottled at the source, without further treatment except for particle filtration. Its composition may vary, and it does not need a consistent mineral content. Mineral water is a type of spring water with stricter requirements. It comes from a recognized, protected ground source and has a consistent composition of minerals and trace elements [62]. The pH levels of the bottled waters ranged from 6 to 8.2, while the hardness values varied between 21 and 1860.1 mg Ca²⁺ L⁻¹. Salinity (Na⁺ + Cl⁻) ranged between 2.5 and 210 mg L⁻¹, and dissolved carbon dioxide ranged between 17 and 1367 mg L⁻¹ (Table S5). All plastic bottles were made of polyethylene terephthalate (PET). However, it was hypothesized that the thickness of the plastic polymer - which correlates with the cost of the bottled water [63] - might influence the concentration of EDCs in the water; therefore, this parameter was also considered (Table S5). After collection, the bottles were transported at room temperature and stored within 1 h in the dark at 4 °C until analysis within 72 h. During sample analysis, quality control was assured by using internal standards, a fresh-made matrix-matched calibration curve and at least 6 matrix-matched quality control samples at 3 concentration levels, i.e. 5.0 (n = 2), 25 (n = 2) and 50 ng L⁻¹ (n = 2).

2.9. Data analysis

2.9.1. Targeted analysis

The identification of individual compounds was based on the accurate mass (*m/z*) of the pseudo-molecular ion (i.e. [M+H]⁺ or [M - H]⁻ based on previous studies [8,64,65]), with a mass deviation of less than 1 ppm, the ¹³C/¹²C isotope profile, and RT relative to the internal standard, with a deviation of ±2.5 % [48,49]. These parameters were

compared to the corresponding reference standard. Confirmation was further ensured by the presence of one (triclosan) or two product ions (all other compounds), with the relative RT of detected peaks within a margin of 2.5 % of the analytes in the matrix-matched samples [55].

2.9.2. Suspect screening

Suspect screening of polar EDCs was performed on full scan data using Compound Discoverer 3.3 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA), within a scan range of 60–900 Da and RT limits of 0.5–10 min, facilitating automated peak alignment, extraction, deconvolution, blank peak filtering, and noise removal. An in-house database was constructed covering 983 compounds identified as having endocrine disrupting potential, which were generated from the European endocrine disruptor list [29], the U.S. TEDX list [66], and literature [67–69], covering additional pharmaceuticals, phthalates, phenols, as well as parabens, amines, etc. The screening criteria included a minimum signal intensity of 1 × 10⁷, a maximum mass deviation of 5 ppm, and the presence of the ¹³C isotope and stable ¹³C/¹²C-ratio. Blank samples (ACN) were employed to subtract noise peaks from the samples of interest. If possible, confirmatory analysis using purchased reference standards (Sigma-Aldrich, Overijse, Belgium) was conducted to ensure accurate compound identification by matching accurate mass (deviation limit <1 ppm), and RT (deviation ± 2.5 %) of the pseudo-molecular parent and product ions.

2.9.3. Statistical approach to water sample analysis

Data analyses considering bottled water samples were performed using Python (version 3.11.7) leveraging several specialized libraries: pandas (v2.1.4) for data manipulation, numpy (v1.26.4) for numerical operations, seaborn (v0.12.2) and matplotlib.pyplot (v3.8.0) for data visualization, and scipy (v1.11.4) for statistical testing. The analytical process encompassed a systematic pipeline designed to visualize, explore, validate, and model the data effectively. A Shapiro-wilk and Levene's test was executed to test normality and equality of variances, respectively. For data with a non-normal distribution and unequal variances, significant differences in the concentration and number of EDCs between plastic and glass bottles were analyzed using the non-parametric Mann-Whitney *U* test. For normally distributed data, a Student's *t*-test was employed. Finally, a linear regression model was used to assess the influence of pH, hardness, salinity, dissolved carbon dioxide, water source (spring versus mineral) and cost of plastic bottled water (€/L) on each individual EDC concentration. The False Discovery Rate (FDR) correction was performed using the Benjamini-Hochberg procedure with correlations considered significant at *q* ≤ 0.05 [70].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Method optimization

3.1.1. Instrumental method

The results of the instrumental method optimization experiment are presented in Fig. 1a and Table S6. A significant effect, with a *t*-ratio > |1.96| and a *p*-value < 0.05, was observed for the sweep gas flow on the summarized, normalized areas across all components. Specifically, higher summarized, normalized areas were obtained at a lower sweep gas flow (2 compared to 5 or 10 a.u.). This may be explained by lower sweep gas flow rates allowing ions to remain longer in the HESI ionization source leading to more complete ionization. The resulting extended interaction may enhance ionization efficiency, exerting stronger signals and thus higher normalized areas [71]. Additionally, a significant effect of the mobile phase starting conditions was noted specifically for pharmaceuticals and industrial chemicals such as phenols and phthalates, with the optimal starting condition being 95 % A (0.1 % NH₄OH in UP water) and 5 % B (0.1 % NH₄OH in ACN). This finding is in line with previous research regarding the detection of phenols and phthalates in aquatic matrices using

Fig. 1a. T-ratio effect diagram highlighting the significance of various instrumental parameters, both overall as for different EDC classes. T-ratio effect bars that extend beyond the 95 % confidence interval (dashed line) indicate a significant impact of the corresponding parameter on the instrumental analysis. Note: triclosan and 3-4-MBC were included in the “all” category, as each constitutes a single-compound class.

UHPLC-Orbitrap-HRMS [46]. Finally, different collision energies were applied to investigate and select the most optimal product ions (MS1 and MS2) (Table 2).

3.1.2. Sample pretreatment

3.1.2.1. Still water. Oasis® HLB SPE cartridges (6 mL, 500 mg, Waters) were chosen based on previous work highlighting their superior performance compared to other cartridges for extracting multi-class EDCs at a broad polarity range from surface water [46,59,65]. The sample pretreatment was further optimized using a Full Factorial experimental design, evaluating the effects of filtration, acidification, and reconstitution solvent type on the extraction efficiency of the 25 target EDCs.

The results of this optimization experiment - both overall and for the individual EDC classes - are shown in Fig. 1b as a T-ratio effect diagram, highlighting the significance of the extraction parameters, and in Table S6, which presents the corresponding T-ratios and p-values. When considering EDCs as one group, none of the parameters had a significant impact on the summarized normalized areas ($t\text{-ratio} < |1.96|$ and $p\text{-value} > 0.05$). However, when categorizing EDCs into subgroups, a significant effect ($t\text{-ratio} > |1.96|$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.05$) was observed for filtration of pharmaceuticals, and for the type of reconstitution solvent to resolve mycotoxins: *i.e.* higher summarized normalized areas were observed without filtration, and the use of ACN/UP water instead of MeOH/UP water, respectively. Based on these results, the final protocol did not include acidification, aligning with prior research indicating no significant impact on extraction recovery for certain EDCs across a pH

Fig. 1b. T-ratio effect diagram highlighting the significance of various extraction parameters, both overall as for different EDC classes. T-ratio effect bars that extend beyond the 95 % confidence interval (dashed line) indicate a significant impact of the corresponding parameter on the extraction process. Note: triclosan and 3-4-MBC were included in the “all” category, as each constitutes a single-compound class.

range of 0–10 [72]. Since filtration with glass fiber filters yielded lower summarized normalized areas - likely due to adsorption, as previously demonstrated for propranolol [73] being attributed to its basic amine groups which are also present in citalopram - this step was omitted, further improving the method's feasibility. Finally ACN/H₂O was used as the final reconstitution solvent. These optimization findings are consistent with earlier studies that have successfully extracted multi-class EDCs from aquatic matrices [69,74].

3.1.2.2. Sparkling water. Results of the sample pretreatment optimization experiment conducted on sparkling water are presented in Fig. S3. Among the tested conditions, ultrasonication for 5 min without acidification, followed by the optimized protocol for still water, proved to be the most effective method for extracting the 25 EDCs. This approach consistently produced the highest and most stable peak heights, yielding a normalized area of 1.00 for 14 out of 25 analytes and a summarized normalized area of 21.6. In contrast, adding formic acid followed by a similar ultrasonication period resulted in lower and less consistent recoveries, most heavily affecting bisphenol A and B, with the lowest summarized normalized area of 20.3. Although extending the ultrasonication to 20 min (with or without acidification) produced comparable summarized normalized areas to the 5-min non-acidified method, it introduced greater variability across analytes - some were efficiently recovered, while others, mostly nonylphenol, bisphenol B, testosterone and propranolol, showed substantially reduced responses (normalized areas <0.70) compromising the reproducibility of the extraction.

3.2. Method validation on still water

Table 2 provides a summary of all validation parameters, including LOQ, LOD, R_{app}, precision, and U. Excellent linearity between a calibration range of 1.0 or 5.0, depending on the established LOQ, and 100 ng L⁻¹ was achieved for all target compounds, with R² ≥ 0.99 and g ≤ 9.21 %, using a weighting factor of 1/x² for optimal fit. LOD values ranged from 0.5 to 5.0 ng L⁻¹. LOQ values ranged between 1.0 and 5.0 ng L⁻¹. Overall, these LODs and LOQs are comparable [26] or better [27, 28] than those reported in previous studies using UHPLC-HRMS for one or more EDCs from a max. of 6 different classes, as presented in Table 1. The somewhat higher LODs observed in this study compared to those reported by Huysman (2017) [26] and Tröger (2018) [27] can be attributed to matrix variability - our samples showed wide differences in hardness, salinity, and dissolved carbon content, which were not reported in other studies - as well as differences in instrumental configuration. Specifically, atmospheric pressure chemical ionization (APCI) is generally better suited than ESI for moderately polar, thermally stable hormones such as estrogens, which may affect sensitivity [75]. Inter-laboratory variability may also play a role - although a large European study reported an inter-lab reproducibility of ~5.5 ng L⁻¹ for estrogenic substances in aquatic matrices using LC-MS/MS, indicating that these methods are fundamentally robust [76]. Given the high resolution of the Orbitrap, such variability may be even further minimized. Furthermore, the obtained LODs for atrazine (3.6 ng L⁻¹) and 4-nonylphenol (1.0 ng L⁻¹) are well over 30 % lower than their respective EQS of 0.6 µg L⁻¹ and 0.3 µg L⁻¹ as specified by CD 2009/90/EC. Evaluation of the within-day R_{app} in full-scan mode demonstrated that all EDCs presented satisfying values between 96.0 and 107 % (50 ng L⁻¹), 97.9 and 105 % (25 ng L⁻¹), and 94.4 and 111 % (5.0 ng L⁻¹). Furthermore, good results were obtained for the between-day R_{app}, ranging between 97.2 and 103 % (50 ng L⁻¹), 98.6 and 104 % (25 ng L⁻¹), and 95.3 and 113 % (5.0 ng L⁻¹). When averaging within- and between-day apparent R_{app}, two compounds - 17β-estradiol (RT 3.52) and acetaminophen (RT 1.16) - consistently showed slightly elevated values (~105 %), likely due to matrix-related ion enhancement or baseline background contributing to the signal [77]. Overall these results match [26] or even exceed [27] those reported in previous studies detecting EDCs by UHPLC-HRMS in

drinking water. The within-day and between-day RSDs for all EDCs were below 18.2 % and 14.5 %, respectively, with 4-MBC being the least precise (showing the highest RSD at 5.0 ng L⁻¹). The lower precision observed for 4-MBC likely relates to its relatively hydrophobic nature, which can cause variable retention in SPE, as well as weaker or less stable ionization efficiency in the mass spectrometer, particularly at very low concentrations [78]. Nevertheless, the values fall within the precision ranges recommended by guidelines [55,60], though those for hormones (≤14 %) and mycotoxins (≤14 %) are somewhat higher than the <10 % typically reported in comparable studies [25,26]. This may reflect the compromises inherent in a multimethod covering diverse analytes, as well as inconsistencies in how precision is calculated and reported across the literature [27]. Results of U were within acceptable limits (i.e. 4.4–35.5 %) in accordance with the European guideline CD 2009/90/EC. These have to the authors knowledge not been calculated in other similar studies, although prioritized by the European Commission [54]. Finally, no interference peaks were observed in blank tap water samples within a 5 % RT margin for all target compounds at their accurate mass, confirming the high specificity of the method. No carry-over was detected in any of the solvent samples (ACN/UP water, 95/5, v/v) injected directly after the highest calibrator (100 ng L⁻¹). Based on the excellent accuracy, precision, stability, detection limits well below regulatory thresholds, and measurement uncertainties compliant with European guidelines - and together with a short runtime and a simple SPE workflow requiring no filtration - this method is deemed highly scalable and well-suited for routine monitoring.

3.3. Cross-validation on sparkling water

Cross-validation results in sparkling water met the performance criteria outlined in SANTE/12682/2019 for 24 out of 25 EDCs. Within-day R_{app} ranged from 91.1 to 119 % at 5.0 ng L⁻¹, 75.4–106 % at 25 ng L⁻¹, and 97.7–104 % at 50 ng L⁻¹, with precision values below 19.6 % (Table 3). For 17β-estradiol, a slightly elevated R_{app} of 123 % was observed at the lowest spiking level, which aligns with the still water method validation being attributed to matrix-induced ionization effects [77]. Nevertheless, the measurements were highly reproducible, with a precision of 0.4 %.

3.4. Sample storage stability

Results of the storage stability study indicated that all EDCs were stable at both concentration levels in still drinking water, yielding a recovery between respectively 88.9 and 120 % (25 ng L⁻¹) and 94.1 and 117 % (50 ng L⁻¹) (Table S7). Standard deviations were below 19.3 %, except for estrone, which displayed a standard deviation of 28 % (Table S7). These findings align with the high stability observed in several groups of EDCs, as reported in prior studies [65,79], and with the somewhat greater variability in estrogen degradation in water, also noted in previous research [80]. Taking previous and current findings into account, it can be concluded that analysis performed within 72 h of cooled storage in the dark is sufficient to avoid loss by degradation for all 25 EDCs included in this targeted methodology.

3.5. Endocrine disrupting compounds in commercially bottled waters in Belgium

3.5.1. Targeted analysis

A total of 17 different EDCs were found across different brands, with concentrations ranging between 61.4 ng L⁻¹ and < LOQ (1.0–5.0 ng L⁻¹) (Table 4). Highest concentrations were found for bisphenol B (C_{max} of 61.4 ng L⁻¹), followed by acetaminophen (C_{max} of 60.2 ng L⁻¹), α-zearalanol (C_{max} of 53.2 ng L⁻¹), 17α-ethinylestradiol (C_{max} of 52.5 ng L⁻¹), dibutyl phthalate (C_{max} of 48.8 ng L⁻¹) and to a lesser extent estrone (C_{max} of 29.3 ng L⁻¹). Maximum concentrations of bisphenol A (20 ng L⁻¹) and 4-nonylphenol (12 ng L⁻¹) were substantially below the

Table 3

Validation results for the limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ), measurement uncertainty (U), and both within- and between-day precision and apparent recovery (R_{app}) are presented for the 25 EDCs assessed during the methodological validation in still water. Superscript values correspond to cross-validation results obtained in sparkling water.

EDCs	LOD/LOQ (ng L ⁻¹)		Within-Day Precision and Recovery						Between-Day Precision and Recovery								
			Theoretical concentration						Theoretical concentration								
			5.0 ng L ⁻¹ , (n = 4)		25 ng L ⁻¹ , (n = 4)		50 ng L ⁻¹ , (n = 4)		5.0 ng L ⁻¹ , (n = 4)			25 ng L ⁻¹ , (n = 4)			50 ng L ⁻¹ , (n = 4)		
			Prec.	R_{app}	Prec.	R_{app}	Prec.	R_{app}	Prec.	R_{app}	U	Prec.	R_{app}	U	Prec.	R_{app}	U
(RSD,%)	(%)	(RSD,%)	(%)	(RSD,%)	(%)	(RSD,%)	(%)	(%)	(RSD,%)	(%)	(%)	(RSD,%)	(%)	(%)			
Hormones																	
Estrone	1.5	5.0	3.9 ^{6.4}	101 ¹¹⁹	4.6 ^{3.7}	100 ¹⁰¹	2.4 ^{2.1}	103 ¹⁰¹	9.9	101	14.3	6.0	98.7	7.0	3.0	101	6.9
17 α -Ethinylestradiol	4.2	5.0	9.6 ^{15.6}	103 ¹¹²	2.1 ^{5.3}	102 ¹⁰⁴	2.3 ^{2.4}	100 ^{99.9}	10.6	107	25.5	5.1	101	11.5	4.7	103	9.9
17 β -Estradiol	1.9	5.0	13.9 ^{9.4}	94.4 ¹²³	4.1 ^{4.3}	105 ^{94.8}	2.0 ^{4.1}	103 ^{98.5}	13.5	109	34.9	3.6	103	7.6	2.7	103	5.9
Progesterone	3.0	5.0	6.1 ^{6.9}	106 ^{95.3}	6.6 ^{1.3}	101 ^{75.4}	1.2 ^{2.4}	99.7 ^{97.7}	10.0	99.9	11.1	4.7	101	8.3	3.8	100	8.3
Testosterone	4.2	5.0	8.9 ^{17.7}	110 ¹¹⁸	3.3 ^{2.6}	101 ¹⁰⁰	3.1 ^{4.2}	99.2 ^{99.9}	11.0	113	32.1	7.7	100	14.2	3.3	102	7.3
Microbial agent																	
Triclosan	0.7	5.0	11.5 ^{8.6}	97.4 ¹⁰⁷	6.9 ^{2.3}	99.1 ¹⁰⁵	1.9 ^{1.2}	102 ¹⁰¹	8.3	99.3	12.4	6.0	99.8	9.6	3.1	103	5.0
Mycotoxins																	
Zearalenone	4.4	5.0	9.9 ^{5.6}	105 ¹⁰⁶	2.0 ^{1.6}	98.0 ^{98.9}	1.9 ^{1.0}	101 ¹⁰⁰	11.7	109	30.3	2.9	101	7.8	1.4	101	4.4
α -Zearalanol	0.5	5.0	10.3 ^{3.5}	108 ¹¹⁵	3.6 ^{5.2}	102 ¹⁰³	2.0 ^{1.4}	100 ¹⁰¹	13.8	98.7	15.3	2.8	103	7.3	8.7	97.2	7.1
Pesticides																	
Atrazine	3.6	5.0	7.4 ^{8.8}	108 ¹⁰²	0.8 ^{0.4}	97.9 ^{97.9}	3.7 ^{0.8}	105 ¹⁰⁰	6.4	106	22.9	2.1	99.2	6	3.2	102	7.2
DEET	2.7	5.0	3.8 ^{19.1}	106 ¹⁰³	0.9 ^{3.4}	103 ¹⁰²	0.9 ^{1.9}	99.3 ¹⁰⁰	6.5	105	16.8	6.7	99.2	12.9	1.5	101	4.5
Fipronil	0.5 ^d	1.0	7.3 ^{12.6}	97.3 ^{98.9}	1.9 ^{3.8}	103 ^{98.1}	4.6 ^{0.2}	106 ¹⁰²	8.9	103	17.8	3.1	102	7.1	4.3	102	8.4
Propiconazole	0.7 ^d	1.0	3.0 ^{6.0}	101 ^{91.1}	5.0 ^{6.9}	100 ^{98.3}	2.3 ^{0.6}	103 ¹⁰²	7.7	108	27.5	3.6	100	7.0	3.2	103	6.2
Pharmaceuticals																	
Acetaminophen	5.0	5.0	7.0 ^{12.1}	110.8 ¹¹⁸	3.3 ^{3.7}	99.0 ¹⁰²	4.2 ^{3.9}	99.2 ¹⁰⁴	8.9	112	27.4	4.8	101	9.9	3.5	101	5.7
Carbamazepine	2.7	5.0	3.4 ^{11.1}	108 ^{94.2}	3.2 ^{5.4}	102 ^{99.4}	8.7 ^{1.1}	97.1 ¹⁰⁰	11.4	95.3	28.4	4.3	101	5.7	5.4	99.8	6.3
Chlorothiazide	3.8	5.0	12.2 ^{14.3}	104 ^{98.2}	3.4 ^{1.8}	103 ¹⁰³	4.1 ^{1.9}	102 ¹⁰¹	11.2	104	18.1	4.3	103	7.4	5.0	99.6	5.7
Citalopram	0.8 ^d	1.0	8.1 ^{6.1}	105 ¹¹⁵	2.4 ^{5.9}	103 ¹⁰⁶	6.1 ^{2.0}	96.0 ^{99.6}	6.1	104	14.3	3.6	103	7.7	2.7	101	5.8
Propranolol	3.3	5.0	4.6 ^{4.4}	104 ^{96.7}	2.9 ^{1.5}	98.7 ¹⁰³	3.1 ^{1.3}	100 ^{98.1}	8.4	100	15.2	2.3	100	5.6	2.3	101	4.9
Phenols																	
Bisphenol A	3.9	5.0	9.3 ^{19.6}	98.9 ¹¹⁵	5.1 ^{1.2}	98.7 ¹⁰⁶	4.0 ^{1.8}	99.0 ¹⁰²	12.5	105	27.1	4.0	101	6.4	7.2	99.8	8.9
Bisphenol B	2.1	5.0	3.5 ^{17.7}	103 ¹⁰³	2.5 ^{3.8}	102 ¹⁰³	1.6 ^{1.1}	102 ¹⁰³	8.1	106	15.6	4.5	101	7.4	2.3	102	5.8
4-Dodecylphenol	4.2	5.0	6.4 ^{3.9}	101 ¹⁰⁵	2.1 ^{1.8}	98.4 ¹⁰¹	1.9 ^{3.9}	102 ¹⁰²	8.7	107	22.7	5.9	104	10.4	10.7	97.9	7.5
4-Nonylphenol	1.0	5.0	4.2 ^{10.9}	104 ¹⁰⁷	4.3 ^{3.5}	102 ¹⁰⁴	2.1 ^{4.1}	104 ¹⁰²	10.3	102	16.4	3.7	102	9.2	10.3	98.3	7.9
Phthalates																	
BBP	2.9	5.0	11.9 ^{6.3}	103 ^{98.4}	3.5 ^{3.1}	99.8 ¹⁰⁴	2.8 ^{3.8}	100 ^{98.2}	9.4	105	17.4	2.7	102	6.2	2.2	101	5.8
DBP	4.9	5.0	15.3 ^{10.6a}	109 ^{102a}	3.6 ^{1.5}	102 ¹⁰²	4.0 ^{0.9}	99.4 ^{99.5}	11.8	112	35.5	2.7	101	8.9	3.9	98.7	9.2
DCHP	1.9	5.0	5.9 ^{5.9}	103 ¹⁰³	3.9 ^{3.3}	105 ¹⁰¹	2.2 ^{1.5}	101 ^{98.9}	8.8	102	16.7	3.0	103	8.0	2.5	102	6.8
Sunscreen agent																	
3-4-MBC	1.0	5.0	18.2 ^{4.6}	107 ¹⁰⁵	2.8 ^{4.3}	100 ¹⁰⁴	5.8 ^{2.4}	107 ¹⁰³	14.5	107	24.5	7.8	98.6	9.5	6.1	102	12.0

Note: Prec. = precision; DEET = diethyltoluamide, BBP = benzyl butyl phthalate, DBP = dibutyl phthalate, DCHP = dicyclohexyl phthalate, 3-4-MBC = 3-4-methylbenzylidene-camphor.

^a Calculations made using concentrations corrected for 5.32 ng L⁻¹ residue in blank.

Table 4

Concentrations in ng L⁻¹ of the retrieved targeted EDCs in 37 frequently used and commercially available bottled still water samples, collected from local supermarkets and beverage distributors in Flanders, Belgium.

Sample	ACE	BBP	Bis A	Bis B	CIT	DBP	DCHP	DEET	4-DPH	ESTRA	ESTRO	EthEST	FIP	4-MBC	4-NPH	TCS	α -ZAL
1	n.d.	< LOQ	8.0	25.4	n.d.	2.5	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	48.5
2	33.0	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	28.3	n.d.	< LOQ	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.
3	39.9	< LOQ	n.d.	10.6	n.d.	9.8	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	6.9	n.d.	n.d.
4	9.1	< LOQ	< LOQ	15.7	n.d.	15.2	< LOQ	n.d.	5.0	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.5	n.d.	n.d.
5	16.1	< LOQ	< LOQ	8.0	n.d.	18.9	n.d.	n.d.	5.1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	< LOQ
6	2.5	< LOQ	n.d.	5.0	n.d.	28.1	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.2	n.d.	n.d.
7	12.8	10.1	n.d.	10.4	n.d.	48.8	n.d.	<LOQ	5.0	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	6.7	n.d.	n.d.
8	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	10.3	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.0	n.d.	n.d.
9	5.9	< LOQ	15.4	26.9	n.d.	2.5	n.d.	< LOQ	< LOQ	n.d.	5.2	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	< LOQ
10	16.0	n.d.	n.d.	6.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.0	n.d.	<LOQ	28.5	< LOQ	n.d.	7.1	< LOQ	n.d.
11	23.2	n.d.	19.5	36.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	<LOQ	5.0	n.d.	5.3	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	7.7	n.d.	22.4
12	43.5	n.d.	19.6	59.3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.1	5.1	n.d.	21.9	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	4.9	n.d.	< LOQ
13	17.7	n.d.	n.d.	10.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	< LOQ	n.d.	<LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	7.9	n.d.	7.6
14	60.2	n.d.	< LOQ	6.3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	6.8	n.d.	n.d.
15	19.6	n.d.	n.d.	14.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.1	n.d.	<LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	6.5	n.d.	n.d.
16	18.0	n.d.	n.d.	6.7	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	8.1	n.d.	n.d.
17	2.5	n.d.	< LOQ	19.4	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	5.5	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	16.4
18	15.4	n.d.	n.d.	7.8	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	5.7	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	27.4
19	21.9	n.d.	n.d.	5.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.2	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	5.0
20	14.0	n.d.	n.d.	6.9	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	6.7	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	7.1	n.d.	n.d.
21	18.1	n.d.	n.d.	5.3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.6	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ
22	9.9	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	2.5	n.d.	n.d.	5.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.
23	7.8	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.
24	2.5	n.d.	7.1	61.4	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	19.9	5.3	n.d.	17.7	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	45.5
25	5.8	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.
26	20.5	n.d.	n.d.	6.5	n.d.	17.5	n.d.	n.d.	5.1	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	10.9	n.d.	n.d.
27	14.6	n.d.	n.d.	9.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	6.7	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	7.0	n.d.	n.d.
28	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	20.8	n.d.	11.4	n.d.	< LOQ	6.6	n.d.	6.2	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	16.0
29	< LOQ	n.d.	9.5	41.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	20.5	5.2	n.d.	29.3	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	12.0	n.d.	53.2
30	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	52.5	n.d.	n.d.	81.8	n.d.	n.d.
31	n.d.	n.d.	11.8	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	30.0	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.
32	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	33.2	n.d.	n.d.	11.7	n.d.	n.d.
33	n.d.	n.d.	30.2	39.6	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	47.9	n.d.	< LOQ	2.5	n.d.	n.d.
34	n.d.	n.d.	14.2	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	34.7	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	< LOQ
35	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	6.3	n.d.	6.4	n.d.	12.2	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	26.3	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ
36	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	5.3	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	< LOQ	n.d.	n.d.
37	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.	n.d.

Note: ACE = acetaminophen, BBP = benzylbutyl phthalate, Bis A = bisphenol A, Bis B = bisphenol B, CIT = citalopram, DBP = dibutyl phthalate, DCHP = dicyclohexyl phthalate, DEET = diethyltoluamide, 4-DPH = 4-dodecylphenol, ESTRA = 17 β -estradiol, ESTRO = estrone, EthEST = 17 α -ethinyloestradiol, FIP = fipronil, 4-NPH = 4-nonylphenol, TCS = triclosan, α -ZAL = α -zearalanol, n.d. = not detected, <LOQ = below the method LOQ but above the LOD.

maximum (guidance) levels set by Europe, *i.e.* 2.5 and 0.3 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$, respectively. With the exception of one brand containing no traces of EDCs, all other bottled waters contained between 2 and 10 different EDCs, with highest detection frequencies for bisphenol B (100 %), 4-nonylphenol (97 %), and 4-dodecylphenol and acetaminophen (86 %). Additionally, no traces of the regulated atrazine and 17 β -estradiol were found. Overall, plastic bottled waters contained significantly higher levels of EDCs than glass bottled waters (Fig. 2), as confirmed by Mann-Whitney *U* test ($p < 0.05$). In particular, benzyl butyl phthalate, bisphenol B, 4-nonylphenol, and acetaminophen were found at significantly higher concentrations in plastic bottles. With the exception of acetaminophen, these findings align with previous studies, suggesting migration of chemicals from plastic packaging into the water [81,82]. OLS regression showed that α -zearalanol concentrations were significantly influenced by water source: mineral water samples contained significantly higher levels of α -zearalanol than spring water ($\beta = 5.81$, $p < 0.001$, FDR = 0.002). This mycotoxin, linked to agricultural activity and also metabolized by humans and animals, may be more prevalent in mineral waters due to their sources being closer to areas impacted by agricultural runoff [65]. After controlling for water source and confirming that no significant interactions existed between water source and bottle type (Table S8), regression analysis showed a significant positive association between cost of plastic bottled water and concentrations of two plastic-derived EDCs: dibutyl phthalate (Estimate = 3.45, $p = 0.0057$, FDR = 0.023) and benzyl butyl phthalate (Estimate = 2.81, $p = 0.0066$, FDR = 0.023) (Fig. 3). These findings suggest that more expensive plastic bottled waters, presumably containing more layers of polymer, contain higher levels of these compounds. However, this interpretation should be viewed with caution, as the limited number of samples per retail source restricts our ability to assess potential confounding by retail origin. Nonetheless, results challenge the common assumptions about exposure equity, indicating that higher-income individuals - who are more likely to purchase premium bottled water - may in fact be exposed to greater levels of certain EDCs through packaging-related contamination [63]. Finally, although bisphenol B showed a negative cost-association (Estimate = -0.43 , $p = 0.047$), the result was not statistically significant after correction for multiple comparisons (FDR = 0.11). No significant relationships with the cost of plastic bottled water were observed for any of the other EDCs (all FDR

>0.29).

3.5.2. Suspect screening

Suspect analysis was conducted by screening full spectrum acquisitions against our in-house database of 983 compounds with potential endocrine disrupting activity (Table S9). Since ESI typically generates molecular ions $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$ or $[\text{M}-\text{H}]^-$, the initial suspect screening focused on these masses, resulting in 120 candidates in ESI-mode and 49 candidates in ESI+ mode. Based on accurate mass measurements (within 5 ppm) and the presence of the ^{13}C isotope and a stable $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ isotope ratio (Fig. 4), 55 chemicals were tentatively identified (See Fig. S4), including 16 cosmetic ingredients (3 hair dyes, 4 surfactants, 3 preservatives, 3 fragrances & 3 UV filters), 12 plastic additives, 6 pesticides, 3 industrial dye products, 3 flame retardants, 3 anti-oxidants, 2 surfactants, 1 pharmaceutical product and 9 other non-classifiable compounds (Table 5) [83–87]. To achieve the highest level of identification (level 1 by Schymanski et al., 2014) [88], reference standards were purchased and analyzed for 10 of the identified candidates. A total of 6 proposed structures were confirmed, *i.e.* 2-hydroxybiphenyl, 3-ethylphenol, decanoic acid, dexamethasone, diethyl phthalate and propylparaben (Table 5), by matching the accurate mass (with a deviation limit of <1 ppm), RT (deviation within ± 2.5 %) and the presence of the ^{13}C -isotope. The detected compounds are closely associated with packaging materials, cosmetics, or pharmaceutical applications. For instance, diethyl phthalate, a common plasticizer, has been linked to bottled water packaging in the past [82]. The presence of 2-hydroxybiphenyl in bottled water is likely due to residues from its use as a biocidal disinfectant in bottling equipment, as its previous role as a post-harvest fungicide on fruits is no longer authorized in Belgium [89,90]. Decanoic acid, used to create esters for fragrances, and propylparaben, a widely recognized preservative, have been extensively used in cosmetics, with propylparaben traced in tap water before [91]. Dexamethasone has also been previously detected in tap water likely as a result of its widespread use in medical treatments [69].

4. Conclusion

This study successfully developed and validated a robust multi-residue method for quantifying 25 targeted EDCs across diverse

Fig. 2. Seaborn plot showing the distribution of EDCs across two types of waters, either originating from glass or plastic bottles. Each subplot corresponds to a different EDC. Bars in the histogram represent the frequency of concentration levels of each compound in either glass (blue color) or plastic bottled water (orange color). The Kernel Density Estimate curve overlaid on each histogram provide a smooth estimate of the concentration distribution for each type of bottled water. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 3. Correlation between benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP) and dibutyl phthalate (DBP) concentrations (log-transformed) and the cost per liter of plastic bottled waters. A moderate positive correlation was observed (Spearman's $r = 0.59$, $p = 0.006$ – 0.007). Each point represents an individual sample; the red line indicates the linear regression fit with 95 % confidence interval (shaded area). The data suggest that more expensive bottled waters, potentially associated with thicker polyethylene terephthalate (PET) packaging, may contain higher phthalate concentrations. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 4. Exemplary presence of the ^{13}C isotope (bottom left) of 3-phenylphenol (top left) in one of the bottled water samples (sampled bottle n° 2), ionized in negative mode.

classes alongside the suspect screening of nearly 1000 potential compounds in drinking water, both still and sparkling, using SPE-UHPLC-HRMS. The still water method exhibited excellent accuracy, precision, and stability, with detection limits well below regulatory thresholds and measurement uncertainties compliant with European guidelines. Cross-validation on sparkling water confirmed robustness for all compounds, although 17β -estradiol showed slightly elevated recovery at the lowest concentration. The omission of a filtration step during extraction, and the short instrumental analysis contributed to the feasibility of this high

throughput method. Subsequent analysis of 37 bottled still water samples identified 17 EDCs, with plastic bottles containing higher concentrations than glass bottles, and spring water significantly differing from mineral water in α -zearalanol, a mycotoxin linked to agricultural activity and metabolized by humans and animals. Notably, bisphenol A and 4-nonylphenol concentrations were well below European guidance levels, and regulated compounds such as atrazine and 17β -estradiol were absent. These findings underscore the efficacy of regulatory measures and the importance of continued monitoring to safeguard public

Table 5

Classification of the 55 chemicals tentatively identified during suspect screening analysis. Compounds were retained based on accurate mass measurements and the presence of the ^{13}C isotope and a stable $^{13}\text{C}/^{12}\text{C}$ isotope ratio. A total of 6 proposed structures (underlined) were confirmed by matching the accurate mass (with a deviation limit of <1 ppm), RT (deviation within $\pm 2.5\%$) and the presence of the ^{13}C -isotope from purchased reference standards. The mass deviation (ppm) and RT (min) for each individual compound are indicated as subscript.

Chemical classification	Chemicals
Anti-oxidants	4-n-butoxyphenol ^a -0.37; 0.98, ethoxyquin 0.45; 4.28, MBB cresol -0.31; 4.68
Cosmetics	2-methylresorcinol -0.73; 3.80, D5 -0.36; 5.89, <u>decanoic acid</u> -0.20; 0.97, DH naphthalene -0.14; 0.80, dibutyl adipate -0.53; 4.25, ethyl paraben 0.03; 7.72, heptyl paraben 0.06; 3.86, hexadecanoic acid 0.37, 3.76, HP butanone -0.15; 3.93, IPM cinnamate -0.10, 3.35, ODA benzoic acid 0; 3.57, octadecanoic acid -0.54; 4.21, octocrylene -0.34; 4.28, PP pyridine -0.31; 5.49, <u>propyl paraben</u> -0.22; 3.92, resorcinol -0.21; 3.71
Dyes (not hair)	acridine -0.33; 4.13, 3-phenylphenol ^b -0.45; 4.18, phenolphthalol -0.08; 3.92
Flame retardants	TB bisphenol A 1.01; 5.87, TCME phosphate 0.09; 4.21, TCME phosphate 0.60; 4.23
Pesticides	<u>2-hydroxybiphenyl</u> ^c 0.02; 4.10, bioallethrin -0.07; 3.54, epofenonane 0.87; 4.23, kinoprene 0.18; 4.49, propazine 2.53; 4.45, resmethrin 0.54; 3.59
Pharmaceuticals	<u>dexamethasone</u> 0.10; 3.45
Plasticizers & polymer production	2-ethylhexanoic acid -0.08; 3.29, 4-cyclopentylphenol ^c -0.07; 4.00, BHPM-pentane -0.27; 3.55, DEHP -0.3; 3.67, DEP -0.19; 3.46, DIBP 0; 4.68, DIHP -0.10; 3.60, DIP -0.18; 6.86, DMP -0.37; 0.85, diphenolic acid 0.60; 1.86, TBE phosphate ^d -0.03; 4.45, TriPDD butyrate ^d -0.02; 3.64
Surfactants	diethanolamine -0.29; 1.42, PFH sulfonate -0.13; 3.65
Other chemicals	<u>3-ethylphenol</u> -0.10; 4.01, 5-indanol -0.21; 0.83, 6-methoxy-m-toluidine -0.15; 2.05, N-benzyl-4-hydroxyaniline -0.68; 3.71, benzo[a]carbazole -0.11; 4.35, CM phenol 0.02; 3.99, DBA phenol 0.48; 5.35, Hpropiophenone -0.20; 1.15, MMD phenylamine 0.42; 4.68
Further classification of cosmetics	Chemicals
Fragrances	<u>decanoic acid</u> , HP butanone, PP pyridine
Hair dyes	2-methylresorcinol, DH naphthalene, resorcinol
Preservatives	ethyl paraben, heptyl paraben, <u>propyl paraben</u>
Surfactants	D5, dibutyl adipate, hexadecanoic acid, octadecanoic acid
UV filters	IPM cinnamate, octocrylene, ODA benzoic acid

Note.

BHPM-pentane = 2,2-bis(4-hydroxyphenyl)-4-methyl-n-pentane; CM = 2-chloro-4-methyl; D5 = decamethylcyclopentasiloxane; DBA = 3-(dibutylamino); DEHP = bis(2-ethylhexyl) phthalate; DEP = diethyl phthalate; DH = 2,7-dihydroxy; DIBP = diisobutyl phthalate; DIHP = di-isoheptyl phthalate; DIP = di-isononyl phthalate; DMP = dimethyl phthalate; Hpropiophenone = 4'-hydroxypropiofenone; HP = 4-(4-hydroxyphenyl); IPM = isopentyl p-methoxy; MMD = 4-methoxy-2-methyl; MMB cresol = 2,2-methylenebis(6-t-butyl-p-cresol); ODA = octyl-dimethyl-p-amino; PFH = perfluorohexane; PP = 4-(phenyl-propyl); TBE = tris(2-butoxyethyl); TB = 3,3',5-tribromo; TCME = tris [2-chloro-1-(chloromethyl)ethyl]; TCME = tris(2-chloro-1-methylethyl); TriPDD butyrate = 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentanediol diisobutyrate.

^a Also used in polymer production.

^b Colorimetric reagent.

^c Also used as flame retardant.

^d Intermediate.

health for which this method, with its broad coverage of multiple classes and an extensive suspect screening list derived from global EDC inventories (Europe, USA, Asia), is highly suitable. Finally, higher retail prices were associated with increased phthalate concentrations. This suggests that more expensive bottled waters - likely packaged in multilayered polymers - contain higher levels of these compounds. Such findings challenge assumptions about exposure equity, indicating that

higher-income consumers, who are more inclined to purchase premium brands, may actually face greater exposure to certain EDCs through packaging-related contamination.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

T. Goessens: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **A. Chen:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **N.N. Truong:** Formal analysis. **S. De Saeger:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **L. Vanhaecke:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **M. De Boevre:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research has been funded by the Research Foundation -Flanders (FWO, 1204324N), the European Research Council (ERC) (HUMYCO, No 946192), the Industrial Research Fund of Ghent University (IOF, F2021/IOF-Equip/014), and Fight Against Cancer (STI, VLK.2025.0002.01). The authors wish to thank Beata Pomian, Malaz Taye, Ellen Van Steenlandt and Kian Caudron for their technical contribution to the study.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aca.2025.344995>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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